

“I’m a strong believer that open access is the way to go for works that have been publicly funded, but there is still a pejorative sense that open access means self-publishing.”

Kain feels that attitudes to open access publishing are slowly changing. This is partly due to the ability for academics to reach a bigger, more diverse audience, the influence that research has when it’s disseminated more widely and the higher citations numbers. However, Kain says many scholars in management positions are still of the view that it is an inferior publishing choice and advise early career researchers against it.

But, Kain thinks the momentum for change is building and that the younger generation of academics will move the debate forward.

“The generation of researchers who were early career five or so years ago and are now coming through to the mid-career stage – they are going to carry a very different view of open access to people of my generation.”

Roger Kain, Professor
of Humanities at the
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Study, University of
London

Why Kain thinks attitudes
to open access publishing
are changing

Higher reader
numbers

The ability to
influence thinking is
greater

Higher citation
numbers

People believe in
equitable access to
knowledge

Attitudes to digital
publishing are
evolving